

Materials Environmental Toxic and Growth Embryos

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Abstract: from Have mercy Embryos in Stomachs Their mothers but God Glory be to Him And come on He is that Behind them And I made them grow And able on Protect them And in same the time Our order God that Maintain On them....where that during Pregnancy Be responsible woman pregnant Double It is from Side On it interest Good health And by feeding it And Side Other Be Responsible on growth The fetus And protect it from all what maybe that It hurts him And here Seeking the mom to to avoid any from Factors that from Its business that Be Performer For the child The little one that Growing in Her guts no Especially Exposure to Air polluted where Suffering Many from Women from Occurrence some Changes in Vision during a period Pregnancy And come back Vision Fog during Pregnancy in Mostly to Changes Hormonal that Lead to Retention Water in Eye And its dryness Usually what Be Temporary And down from By yourself itself after birth But in some Sometimes maybe that Be Changes in Vision during Pregnancy because of poisoning Pregnancy or Hyper activity gland Thyroid or disorder in Levels sugar Blood...may You are exposed woman pregnant For many from Problems Health especially in Months First from Carry it what threatens Her health And safety The fetus on end whether And we remain condition from Anxiety intense Control On it during that Period with Feeling Without certainty And stress from all purpose healthy new To be exposed for him that usually what Lead Problems Pregnancy And health General in Months First to Implications Dangerous may It is interpreted in end The destination to Abortion And a loss The fetus So from essential on woman that Track some Tips in order to Includes stabilizing Pregnancy And prevention itself.from any Developments Healthy no Thank you Its consequences..and that more what It is running By God pregnant during a period Pregnancy he health Her fetus And his safety So it works on create roadblock between The fetus And dangers the environment Surrounding There is Toxins Interface maybe that affect on health The fetus in womb His mother And it can For mother to forbid This is amazing Toxins from Access To him on road limit from Exposure she has that better means To limit from Exposure For toxins Environmental he to understand what Hey Toxins The one present from About us And it can that affect on health The fetus And it indicates Studies to that Pesticides that Contains on Materials Chemical harsh form danger The biggest on The fetus And caused Nausea And vomiting For women pregnant as form The vapors that graduation from Paint Varnish Wood Harm on The fetus To contain it on Materials may Cause ruin with The fetus Also Should ask products Cleaning The village like Ovaries or Ammonia The one present in Powders Clothes And detergents the bathroom during a period Pregnancy Given Its effects Negativity on lung The fetus And Side Other to caution Scientists in Sweden from Use Perfumes Women's during a period Pregnancy Because it is may Lead to infection Births Males With knowledge after that It was completed discovery presence Levels High from Materials Chemical Cause Science in Formula Types Well known from Perfumes And products Beauty And remember Research that it during a period Pregnancy Increase sense smelling when the mom In a way multiple And it must On it if I inhaled any scent For the material Caustic or Harmful that move away on Immediately until no gets hurt Her fetus.

Keywords: Fetal malformations, Materials toxic, Environmental pollution, Environmental waste, Industrial waste.

Introduction

The relationship between environmental toxicants and fetal development is through the influence of various environmental toxicants on fetal development through the potential harmful effects of environmental toxicants on prenatal development of both the embryo and the fetus as well as pregnancy complications. The human embryo or fetus is relatively vulnerable to adverse conditions in the mother's environment. Poor fetal conditions often cause varying degrees of delay in the physical and mental development of the developing child. Although some variables occur as a result of genetic conditions related to the father, many are brought directly from environmental toxins to which the mother is exposed. All humans are susceptible to the effects of exposure to toxic substances (poisons). However, children are more vulnerable than adults because of their small bodies and special behavioral habits. Children consume more food and water relative to their weight, and thus the body absorbs toxins more easily and is less able to excrete them. For example, the bodies of young children absorb four to five times more than adults, which leads to developmental impairment, especially in the lungs, brain, immune system, and fertility, which are particularly affected by environmental changes in childhood.(Agathokleous, 2022; Röllin, 2022) These risks affect all children, including in economically advanced countries. However, the problem is exacerbated by factors linked to poverty and other forms of marginalization (White & Gala, 2022). Poor health associated with economic deprivation reduces children's ability to resist the effects of toxins, especially when children are malnourished (Wakefield-Rann, 2021), while poor regulation of industry and agriculture from malnutrition in poorer countries allows for higher levels of toxins in the places where children live, learn and play (Elbehiry et al, 2021). Children have a higher susceptibility to exposure and are more sensitive to toxic substances, making them more vulnerable than adults and may not have the potential to Lag These effects can be passed on from generation to generation and children have the right to(Thomas et al 2019) Under the Convention on the Rights of the Child, children have the right to live, learn and grow in an environment that facilitates access to health, play and education and is free from undue risks. However, toxic substances violate these rights every day, especially in the air, water, soil and consumer products .I am sick Which harms the Millions From children all over the world(Woodruff et al., 201) .

Exposure For metals Toxic Suppresses growth The fetus:-

Many from Minerals Able on crossing Placenta or changing Her job and Prove number growing from Studies show that Minerals Toxic Coming from sources like Food polluted And water Drinking And the air And dust Polluted is widespread. in the environment And it can For many From it that Express Placenta or change job Placenta what Contributes in curb growth The fetus.(Gundacker & Hengstschläger, 2012)And revealed Shah-Kulkarn et al., (2020)how maybe that Affects Exposure before birth For mix from Minerals Common In a way negative on fetal growth and that Exposure D For mix complicated from several Minerals in time one Which may Interact with each other And it can that Be Domains Exposure Narrow in group one only For metal specific Therefore Our goal was he Look via Groups Population Miscellaneous Multiple with Types Different from Exposure until It is understood better For a leech Response Complete For the dose For some This is amazing Materials Chemistry in Context Mixture The biggest" He conducted(Howe et al., (2022)Analyze to Environmentally For the mix from Effects Mineral on growth The fetus and collected Data from third Groups Miscellaneous geography Demographically in States United Groups participate existing in New significant Bashayer And Los angels and Puerto Rico in Effects Environmental On the program results health The child And he is program My research Supported by Institutes National For health Which He studies Group effects Wide from Effects Environmental Early on health The child And its growth And using approach statistical new to examine Researchers Links between seven Minerals Rumor Existence And it is Antimony And cadmium And cobalt Mercury Molybdenum Nickel And tin It was completed Measure it in1002sample from pee the mom collected during Pregnancy And

weight when birth with regards to age Pregnancy as They did By investigation in Differences potential between Groups And gender A For children She said Doctor How“Result Most Consistently that We got it To her she that Antimony And he is metal not thoughtful He was Related Low the weight when birth with regards to age Pregnancy in all Groups Third And in all from Males And females what indicates to that it may Affects Negatively on growth The fetus Therefore We want to set Sources Home To be exposed For this The element until We can from Help in reduction this Exposure To prevent The effects Harmful on growth The fetus in This is amazing Groups Population Different .

And on way Example may Come back Concentrations Antimony Top that It was noticed in Groups Los angels and Puerto Rico to Its locations Urban where Known pollution Air Related By passing The star on corrosion Brakes That he is source important To be exposed for antimony like Stations burn Coal And incinerators Waste And in The counterpart may Be Water Packaged Source Suitable To be exposed for antimony For groups Third.And in when that Researchers Define some Links Collective or Associated By sex For many from Minerals Other that Done Her study as She says How Lost They lacked to consistency that Seen For results Antimony And he is what It means that there need For more from Search She pointed out How to They are They hope in procedure study greater in the future Includes More from Groups until It is done Empowerment from Look more in what pays This is amazing Contradictions And they understand In a way better Differences potential because of Geography or Features Population Other And it was proven Studies that growth The fetus Related Good health Futuristic Children who They are born Young comparison At age Pregnancy They have Rates higher from Deaths children My talk birth And they are more susceptible To get injured Weakly perception Nervous in Childhood And diseases the heart And the vessels Bloody in time Later from life.

Impact Recognition For pollutants Environmental on Pregnancy And the newborn:-

maybe that Causes Exposure before birth For pollutants Environmental Toxic in Impact on growth The fetus because inhalation that Pollutants may hurts lung The fetus And Causes in non completion Its growth And the possibility Occurrence Abortion or death The fetus It includes Pollutants Environmental:The vapors and materials Chemical Toxic And smoking (Goriainova et al., 2021)

that impact Exposure For pollutants Environmental on Pregnancy And the newborn He is on the next:-

- 1- **low the weight when birth:** affect Pollutants in flow Blood to Placenta where It is Pregnant women more susceptible For pollutants Which may Increase from Infections liner the womb And danger Exposure To decrease weight The fetus after birth And that For its effect on activity The device The immune And my cells Placenta Which Affects in flowBlood and the elements Food to The fetus And problems The device Respiratory And paralysis Cerebral And disability Growth As a result possibility Occurrence Deformities in growth brain I have The fetus.

2- **birth Early:** maybe that Causes Exposure For pollutants Secondly Oxide Sulfur And first Oxide carbon in Third the first from Pregnancy in possibility Occurrence Risks Healthy With placenta I have pregnant while in Late Pregnancy maybe that Lead Pollutants to response Inflammatory may Cause Labor Early. (Ghazi et al., 2021).

Which maybe that Affects on The child By the way Next:-

- problems in Breathing in Year First with risk Injury With asthma.
 - risk Committed death The baby Surprise.
 - risk Occurrence problems in Growth like Paralysis Cerebral And problems Hearing And sight And backwardness Mental.
 - Difficulties Learning And danger Injury With diseases And cases Chronic like disorder loss Attention And excessive Activity
- 3- **infection The child With autism in phase Childhood:** risk Injury With autism It increases with more Exposure For pollutants where It is Pregnant women Exhibitions more For pollutants in Third the third from Pregnancy, They have risk greater For birth children Infected With autism Weakness in the focus.
- 4- **Injury With asthma:** Connected pollution Air With problems The device Respiratory like asthma And diseases the heart And the vessels Bloody And cancer Lung I have I found Studies that Exposure before birth To pollute Air may Affects on growth Lung I have The fetus And risks Injury With asthma in phase Childhood.
- 5- **Complications Pregnancy:** Related Exposure For pollution Increase Risks Occurrence Complications Pregnancy especially flaw Third the first from Pregnancy And it can that Harm This is amazing Complications By mother And the fetus And more Risks Exposure For childbirth Early And not completion growth Lung I have The fetus And problems The device Respiratory Long Rangelike asthma And sensitivity(Sherratt, 2022).

To forbid or reduction Complications Exposure For pollutants Environmental

He should To avoid Pollutants Environmental wear pregnant Mask For the face when Exit in Air The dew Q no You can Women Pregnant women usually Control in Levels pollution around Their homes or Places Their work And with that there some Things that maybe For mother Doing With it To reduce Effects Pollutants From it(Mukherjee et al., 2021)

1. wear mask For the face when Exit in Air The shot.
2. Eat Meals Healthy Rich With vitamins And boosters Immunity.
3. Eat Vitamins And the supplements Food before birth.
4. an experience Use device To purify Air At home.

5. agriculture plants To purify Air in the home and Stay away on Smoke.
6. wear mask For the face when Use products Cleaning or Paint And not Allow For any person By smoking inside the home.

Materials Environmental Toxic And its effects:

Materials that Proven that it Harmful In a way private she Lead(that It was completed Store it in bones the mom)Smoke Cigarettes , And alcohol , Mercury(material Toxic Nervous consume from flaw Fish)Second oxide carbon , And radiation Ionizer(Harper, 2022).Alcohol:may Leads Eat Alcohol during Pregnancy to group from Disturbances known on behalf of Disorders ghost Alcohol embryonic More dangerous This is amazing Symptoms he Committed The fetus Alcoholic(Sessa and others 2022)

- 1- **smoking Tobacco:** may Facing The fetus The exposed To smoke Tobacco before birth group Wide from Difficulties Behavioral , And nervousness , and physical , Includes Effects Harmful The paste , rupture Placenta , Premature birth Early And low The packages when birth , flaws birth Physical palate The cleft etc low in Jobs Lung , more risk Deaths Infants(Venkatesh et al., 2021).
- 2- **Lily:** component Mercury And methyl Mercury Looks like For mercury may cause Risks Poisoning With mercury during Pregnancy Methyl Mercury , contaminated Food Marine And fish Water The sweet one in all around0the world known By producing it antiquities Oh Harmful on The device Nervous , Especially during growth brain It is considered Eat Fish he Source Main To be exposed For mercury I have Humans And Contains some Fish on amount Enough from Mercury To attach Damage By device Nervous The developing For chewing or The fetus , Which Leads in some Sometimes to Disabilities in Learning There is Mercury in Types Many from Fish But it is mostly what There is in some Fish The big one It happened One of Cases Documented good Oh on Eat Mercury on range wide gesticulate Followed by from Complications on growth Embryos in 50s The century Twenty in Gulf enamel They died In Japan It was completed Discharge Methyl Mercury user from before lonliness Industrial close For industry Plastic in waters bay enamel what So where I continue in eat it regularly Many from The villagers who They use Fish that Live in Gulf As an element My food essential.after that A little bit It started Many from Population Who Consume Meat Loaded With mercury They suffer antiquities Negative from Eat poison And with that effect Mercury In a way private on Women Pregnant women And their embryos Which led to to rise an average Abortion He was For infants Survivors who They were exposed For mercury inside the womb Rates High Very from Disabilities Physical And Few And also Deformities Physical resulting on Exposure in the womb flaw Stages Home For growth Physical For the fetus Advise administration Food And the medicine American Agency protection the environment Women Pregnant women Without Eat fish Father sword , Your fish Shark, Your fish Mackerel , And your name Father fund and the limit from Consume tuna primogeniture (Tuna White to 6 deaths or less in The week It is assumed that to rise Levels Mercury in children My talk birth in Gaza arise from arms War and that Exposure For mercury during Pregnancy may He causes also flaws Oh in Parties(Al-Sulaiti et al 2022).
- 3- **Lead:** smell to The effects Harmful To be exposed For lead in Pregnancy Abortion , And low the weight when birth , And delays Nervousness , Poverty Blood , He got sick brain , And paralysis , And blindness And it is growth The device Nervous For the fetus Especially susceptible For poisoning shot..It was noticed poisoning nervous I have children Women Exhibitions a result For ability Lead on crossing roadblock Placenta It is considered Go some Lead Accumulated in Bones in Blood during Pregnancy source anxiety private For pregnant women and I submitted Many from Studies loll to on that it until exposure the mom The depression For lead Leads to Occurrence inability intellectual And my behavior I have children(Priftt & Bimi, 2022).

- 4- **Dioxin:** It remains Dioxin and vehicles Similar To in Air for a while Long It is spreading on range wide So I have all the people Some from Dioxin in Their bodies Connected Exposure inside the womb For dioxin and vehicles Similar With dioxin With changes Evolutionary Hidden on The fetus Includes Effects on The child Later in life Changes in Jobs Liver , And levels Hormone gland Thyroid , And levels Cells Blood White , And low Performance in Tests Learning And intelligence(Martínez et al., 2022).
- 5- **pollution Air:** maybe To pollute Air that Affects looting Oh on Pregnancy Performing to Rates higher from Births Early And disability Growth And problems the heart and lungs between Infants may Cause Vehicles like first oxide carbon Second oxide Sulfur , Second oxide Nitrogen in damage adult if I inhaled it the mom pregnant where Found correlation between your to from low weight birth , And childbirth Early , And disability Growth inside the womb Early And disability Growth And problems the heart and lungs between Infants may Cause Vehicles like first oxide carbon Second oxide Sulfur , Second oxide Nitrogen in damage adult if I inhaled it the mom pregnant where Found correlation between your to from low weight birth , And childbirth Early , And disability Growth inside the womb And deformities Moral And exposed The fetus To pollute Air And despite that pollution maybe Spotted it Almost in all place Then there sources Specific Well known By launching it For materials Toxic And it must that avoid it that It is possible these who They want that They remain We are done relative Oh from Materials Toxic.Includes This is amazing Materials no It is confined on Factories Steel , And stations to treat Waste/Water , And incinerators Sewers , And stations manufacturing Cars , And refineries Oil , And stations manufacturing Materials Chemical(Brodie, & Silberholz, 2021).

maybe To control on pollution Air that Be Difficult on way Example in Los Angeles I put Regulations To control in pollution By putting some Laws on Emissions Industrial And the vehicle where I did Improvements To meet This is amazing Regulations And despite This is amazing Improvements Still Area no Fulfill By standards Federalism For ozone and particles minute what Approaching from 150,000 birth to speak all general in Los Angeles Therefore Then any antiquities To pollute Air on Growth Human inside the womb form source anxiety big For those who They live in This is amazing Area((Wedderburn et al., 2022) Fine particles consist of a mixture of pollutants that remain in the air and that vary depending on Area And this Particles Small grandfather Oh range Its diameters between 10 Micrometer or less and 2.5 Micrometer or less She can easily Login to Lungs where showed Particles minute Related With diseases And deaths Respiratory Cardiac Acute as Show Growth inside the womb Influential with particles minute led to results not Healthy on growth Embryos like growth The fetus The weak or slow And more Illness Embryos And their deaths I found study from general 2012 that Exposure for particles minute the 2.5 It varies. Differently Sweat/Ethnicity , the age And also the condition Social And economic Which Leads to exposure some Population For results Healthy Negative greater because of pollution Environmental Especially While Related with particles minute. (Martenies et al., 2022).

6- **pollution The seas to threaten For pregnant women And her child:-** did not Limited pollution in The era present on Air but rather spread To include The seas that Covering three Quarters space The ball The floor Which constitutes to threaten Oh For its residents from wealth Animal Fish And for humans who They eat it so Move on Toxins and pollutants in the end from the sea via fruits the sea to Their bodies...And there several sources To pollute The seas and oceans like:Water resulting on Factories that Be Maqamah on Beaches The seas or almost From it And it is done Throw it In it And water Sewers that Pour in the sea , And casting Garbage And the waste In it , And water Rivers that Be polluted And bear Pollutants To pour it in the sea.And sources pollution also Pollutants existing in Air Which Download to waters The seas directly or with Rain Fallen , I preferred Ships And boats , and operations Industrial that It is done in the sea like prospecting on Oil And extract it(Kalair et al., 2021

Types of pollutants:-

Vehicles Hydrocarbon:The most important of which is Oil And its derivatives, Which receive from Ships And planes that Express Oceans as Includes Incidents Leakage Oil from Carriers petroleum or Wells prospecting(Ajibade et al., 2021).

Pollutants Food(nutrient pollution):And he spoke when rise rate Materials The feeder in waters The seas a result flow Fertilizers from waters Rivers that Pour In it It increases Relatives Nitrogen And phosphorus Which Leads to more growth Algae in The seas In a way enormous And a problem Algae that it consume a lot from Oxygen from water The seas Which Leads to low Levels Oxygen in The seas The order that Leads to death Fish and beings Marine as that some Types Algae Excrete Poisons kill Fish minerals Heavy:like Lily And lead And cadmium Which from Its effects Occurrence damage intense In the brain And the device Nervous

Materials Radioactive: And enter waters Oceans a result throw Waste Nuclear In it And experiences Nuclear and casting Water that used To cool Reactors The pearl in ocean And it leads Materials Radioactive to cause disturbance Genetic And the injury With cancer I have Humans.

pollution Al-Mercury and Pregnant women:

when Enters The Scent to waters Rivers Or the seas Then bacteria present Naturally in Water Transform it to Mbethel Lily" This The complex Easy Absorb it from before Ahsam Humans Which Makes them susceptible For its effects Toxic And then Enters Lily turn The pyramid Food For fish The fish Small Contains on concentration I am done From him And eat it Fish The big one But The last no It is spent on Mercury or Put it up from Her bodies Which Leads to Gather it in Her bodies The result that Fish The big one like Tuna Your fish Father sword Your fish Shark And mackerel He is concentration The Zeniq in Her bodies more By ten Thousands weakness from His focus in Creatures Surrounding With it.And when He eats Humans Fish that It contains on The screaming They are They are exposed risk Toxic so Affects on brain And the device Nervous And it is Exposure For the heretic Dangerous In a way private on Pregnant

women And children Little ones And even Concentrations Low from Lily that It arrives to Embryos in Stomachs Her mothers And children may Affects on development The child It includes this Delayed Walking And late Speech And difficulties Learning But exposure The fetus For concentrations Big from Lily in stomach His mother It includes Its complications like:Backwardness Mental And paralysis Cerebral And deafness And blindness But with regards For adults Then the focus High from Lily Leads to:problems in Fertility And difficulties in Control on pressure Blood And move in Fingers And loss Sight And problems in the heart And recommends administration Food And the medicine American Women Pregnant women And breastfeeding women Avoid four Types from Fish rise In it Levels Lily And it is Brushes , Father sword , fish The tile and(tilefish), fish Mackerel as Recommend Without Eat more than six ounces(ounce One equal28Grams from Tuna White weekly.

impact pharmaceutical in The fetus: -

Arrive pharmaceutical that take it pregnant to The fetus on road Placenta that Expresses From it Food And oxygen The two necessary To grow The fetus where maybe that affect pharmaceutical that It is done take it without consultation. The doctor While Next:go directly to The fetus Causing some Damages And problems in Growth And development Physical And the mental or until Death...And it can that change job Placenta Usually what Cause narrow Vessels Bloody So gets loss in numbers Oxygen and materials The feeder to The fetus may Cause shrink. Muscles the womb Which Leads to Narrowing diphtheria on The fetus or birth Early.

the fear from Eat Medicines: -

not from Security Stop on Eat any Medicines Medical until It is done speaking to The doctor about Pregnancy and treatment; where that Stop Surprise may It follows attic damage on the mom And the fetus(like:Stop on Eat Medicines pressure The team Without Back to The doctor maybe that Leads to Injury Poisoned Pregnancy..

impact pharmaceutical during stages Pregnancy:-

- 1- **Third the first:-** she Period that It starts In it Be Cells The fetus and its members And it is abundant during This is amazing Stage Occurrence Deformities For embryos So He prefers non Eat any medicine what this pharmaceutical that Prove Its safety For pregnant women

- 2- **Third the second:** what It's gone Members Nostalgia in This is amazing Stage ongoing By growth But it is It is less gravity from the previous.
- 3- **Third the third:** in This is amazing Stage Be may Completed most Members The fetus except brain and members reproductive So He should caution from Eat what Affects in level Hormones And avoid Eat what may He causes problems in brain(like:Drugs or pharmaceutical Psychological.(Rytting et al,2022)

Types pharmaceutical Security Use it during Pregnancy:-

- 1- **Supplements Food:** mostly what You need it pregnant To compensate deficiency The star on lack Eat Food The rich With elements Food In addition to a guarantee Supply The fetus To grow In a way sound Usually what behavior from before The doctor in beginning Pregnancy
 - 2- **Medicines Diseases Chronic:** like The hill Diabetes pressure blood, and others where that it no Bad from treatment This is amazing Diseases And control On it And spend Treatment Suitable from before The doctor.
- Painkillers pain:(like: Paracetamol)where after Usage Average she has after consultation The doctor Our security during Pregnancy
- 3- **Medicines Nausea And vomiting:**after Use vitamin for1from pharmaceutical Safe And effective For this Symptoms especially in Third the first from Pregnancy
 - 4- **Antibiotics Vitality:** some Antibiotics Vitality from family Tensilin And Cephalosporin and azithromycin It is Safe during Pregnancy.
 - 5- **Vaccines during Pregnancy** (like:Vaccine Measles German but from side last It is Vaccines The fortified And seasonal(like:Vaccines flu)Safe during Pregnancy as Should to feed Pregnant women in Third the second or the third With vaccine flu For protection from Injury With it especially in season Its spread In addition to importance take Vaccine Tetanus Protection the mom And the child when birth where Far away risk infection The newborn With illness Tetanus that may It is happening Result Injury Polluted or microbe during practical birth between The week27and36from Pregnancy:during a period Pregnancy He should to avoid The slugs that Contains on Viruses Alive.
 - 6- **Salts shower:** may Contains some Salts pelvis shower on Many from Vehicles Chemical that may Lead to expansion Muscles And unlock Her contractions Which Cause Abortion or birth Early or that Contains on group from Drugs Made from Materials Different that may Cause narrow Vessels Bloody Which Reduces amount Spend Oxygen And food that gets On it The fetus(2021From Alberto).
 - 7- **Real Estate Opium (Poor thing And drugged For pain) :** used Materials Opium during Pregnancy To relieve pain(like:Morphine)But it is Cause also Feeling Adult With numbness In addition to that Usage Excessive she has maybe that Leads to Addiction On it where Easy crossing This is amazing Real Estate to The fetus on road Placenta So may Show symptoms withdrawal after3hours to4days per from the mom And the child after birth with that rarely what Leads Use Materials Opium from before The doctor to flaws Moral as that Use it during Labor maybe that affect In the longing and weakens his ability to breathe after birth, but if it is necessary during labor, it will be given in the lowest doses, but the use of other types of illegal opioids (such as: heroin) increases the risk of complications during pregnancy.)like:AbortionPremature birth, small birth weight or incomplete growth of the baby)(short \$ Destavo 2022)

Alcohol during Pregnancy:-

that drink Alcohol during Pregnancy he the reason President For the flaws Moral I have Embryos(like:flaws in features face , Small Head , non adequacy growth brain Disability mental, And not growth the heart)And in Condition did not Show any flaws Moral No Still there flaws in Behaviors(like:Behavior Hostile , disorder And lack alert)as that it doubles risk Abortion And in a lot from

Sometimes He is weight Births less Much from Average Natural In addition to probability death children after birth In a while Short . (et al., 2022 Hur.) .

Conclusion: -

1. If awoman plans to become pregnant while working in factories producing foetal toxic metals,it is best to leave the job,at least during the pregnancy, to prevent the loss of nostalgia.
2. Mothers removal from environmental contaminants from polluted air such as cigair and car smoke,contaminated water and fish contaminated with mercury and lead in the vicinity of nuclear plants,and contaminated soil is not cultivated because they affect plant life,human food,and lead to featal mutations,fetal death,organ loss,and major carcinogenicity.
3. During the first trimester of pregnancy,the mother is as far away as possible from all medicines,such as chemical and herbal medicines, and is satisfied with those prescribed by the gynaecologist,such as vitamins and minerals, which are necessary for complete fetal development.
4. Avoidance from alcoholic beverages, drugs,stimulants,and attention to healthy food,as well as the physical and psychological well being of the pregnant woman in order to preserve the future fetus from autism,epilepsy,madness,mongol,and organ loss if we do not lose the whole fetus.

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